

doi:10.5281/zenodo.19789382

Boko Hamram Insurgency: It's Impact On Teachers' Job Performance In Colleges Of Education In North - East Zone Of Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study was designed to investigate the performance of teachers during and after Boko Haram insurgency. The activities of Boko Haram in northern parts of Nigeria have led to the destruction of public residential buildings, schools and colleges and killing of teachers and school children. Structured questionnaire was used to collect the data and later analyzed using mean and standard deviation respectively. The study showed that activities of Boko Haram instil fear, destroy personal properties and demoralize them, increase traffic congestion, psychological trauma among others. The State government in collaboration with the Federal Government should be intensify effort towards curbing the menace of insurgency and also the need to rebuild, rehabilitate and protect school facilities, teachers, and students in affected areas when normalcy is returned as recommended by the study.

Keywords: Boko Haram insurgency, teachers, school children

INTRODUCTION

The threat to education from Boko-Haram attack should be seen in the wider problems of the impact of conflict in general on the degradation of educational or prevention of education development. The immediate impact of the attacks include the loss of lives, injury, abduction of students, teachers personal and damage of buildings and facilities most typically due to burning. For instance, the education system lost 85 schools in north eastern Borno affecting nearly 120,000 student. After a spate of attacks by Islamic militants in an area (the guardian, 2014). More than 200 school girls kidnapped on the night of 14 April, 2014 these girls missing at the time of this work. Report has it that girls have been forced into marriage with members of Boko Haram with a reputed 'bride price' of N200 (Wikipedia and encyclopedia 2019 www.encyclopedia.com/girls-force-into-marriage-by-members-of-boho-haram) Of course it is a known fact that early marriage hinder girls child's education. These attacks have forced the affected state government to close down the schools for a prolonged period. The school closing could have far reaching consequence, include ending the education of some student in a region where few ever have the opportunity to get to high school.

Teachers' job performance focus on (a) teachers' ability to master content subject matter or the teaching methods they employ, (b) duration in terms of the number of hours of training and the number of weeks or months over which training is provided, and (c) an activity format that is integrated into the daily work of teachers rather than removed from the context of direct public school teaching. This implied that activities rely mostly on element which has impact on teacher job performance in public and private schools in Nigeria. Adeyemi (2008) stressed that the teachers' job performance could be measured

through the annual report of the teachers' activities in terms of lesson planning, lesson presentation, teacher involvement in extracurricular activities, school discipline, supervision, and teachers' mastery of the subject matter.

Amin et al (2013) mentioned that teachers are the backbone of an educational activity. The success and failure of educational activities highly depend on teachers' job performance. Their performance is directly linked to process and product of education. Therefore, the performance of teachers is emphatic for the improvement of education. According to Amin et al (2013) performance may be described as "an act of accomplishing or executing a given task". It could also be described as the ability to combine skillfully the right behavior towards the achievement of organizational goals and objectives. Amin et al (2013)) states that teachers' job performance can be described as "the duties performed by a teacher at a particular period in the school system in achieving organizational goals. Amin et al (2013) further added that teachers' job performance is determined by the workers' level of participation in the day to day running of the organization. There are some factors which contribute to teacher's job performance. Some of such factors are as satisfying the learners through his teaching style and quality, part of teaching, performance of other assignments as assigned by the Principal and the department, (i) Management of class discipline, (ii) students' motivation and improvement of their academic Performance and (iii) Interaction with students, parents, colleagues and high officials. From an educational point of view, assessment is a process that characterizes a school system.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

In order to achieve the goals and objectives of the educational system, there has to be an appropriate and conducive school environment to ensure teacher job performance in the schools but reverse is the case where Nigeria has been under siege from Boko haram terrorists since 2009, the escalation of the Boko Haram insurgency in Nigeria has had increasingly harmful impacts on the teachers' job performance in North east, Nigeria. Abdulrasheed, Onuselogu and Obioma (2015) stated that from the year 2009, and following the assumption of a new leader, the insurgent group has continued to unleashed violence and began what can best be described as the "soft target" killing unarmed patriotic civilian population of Borno states, forcefully abduction of schoolgirls and women, sporadic shooting, and bombings of public places.

About seven (7) million Nigerians majority of which are children, have been internally displaced and exposed to frequent Boko haram attack, which has implications for their academic achievement and mental health, teachers are rarely assessed and provided with poor academic performance as a result of often forced school closure and vandalization of school facilities as reported by UNICEF (2016). By implication this has played a paramount role in weakening the enrollment and teachers' job performance in the affected states. Atsua and Abdullah (2015) stated that in Maiduguri which shares a border with Yobe and Adamawa States, life is full of insecurity; fear has become part of the people in the affected states. Everybody is asking which area is going to be attacked next. Is it his/her area? Boko Haram activities have greatly affected amenities like schools, houses, hospitals, markets, electricity, etc. Secondary schools in Borno State, for instance, have greatly affected teachers' job performance, almost all the secondary schools in areas affected by the insurgent attacks have been closed which affected the school facilities, students' enrollments, attendance, teachers absconding and teachers' job performance. Atsua and Abdullah (2015) further commented that the state government has attempted to relocate the affected schools in the affected to State capitals, but facilities to accommodate the large number of students are inadequate as some of the existing schools in the State capital have been converted to camps for internally displaced persons. Atsua and Abdullah (2015) observed close discussion with students and teachers affected by the insurgents revealed the devastated impact the activities of Boko Haram had on them ranging from destruction of school facilities, forced school closure and loss of teachers and students' lives which also affected teachers' job performance in the affected states.

An investigation by Justino (2010) into the impact of armed conflict on teaching and learning revealed the destruction of infrastructure, absence of teachers, reductions in schooling capacity and fear of more attacks. All these are counterproductive and may work against learning with students and as factor

militating against teachers' job performance in Colleges of Education. Brendan (2010) confirmed that attacks on schools has lead teachers in to giving their job off or flee the area, or even the In the north eastern region of Nigeria, many teachers were forced to leave their community because of the increasing threat from Boko Haram where Continuing assassinations of teachers and the issuing of death threats has inevitably affect teachers' concentration and frame of mind for teaching. Insecurity has compromised the ability of teachers to perform teaching job efficiently.

Boko Haram insurgents severely undermine the students' school enrollment, students' school attendance and level of school infrastructure and educational outcomes of children in northeastern Nigeria in general. Adebayo (2014) stated that views vary on the impacts of Boko Haram on schools and teaching/learning process. Teachers and students reported in areas of fear, anxiety, and loss of concentration in class among others while principals reported on delayed in processing administrative duties, diminished staff punctuality, delayed graduation, disruption of academic calendars and voluntary withdrawal of students leading to reduction in schools internally generated revenue. Adepelumi (2018).

More than 2,000 people, many of them female, have been abducted by the group, many of their schools from the beginning of the conflict. HRW (2016) confirmed that Thousands more students and teachers have been injured, some in deadly suicide bombs in the same period. Between 2009 and 2015, attacks in northeastern Nigeria destroyed more than 910 schools and forced at least 1,500 to close. By early 2016, an estimated 952,029 school-age children had fled the violence. They have little or no access to education, likely blighting their future for years to come. HRW (2016) interviewed 215 people – including 99 teachers, 31 students, 36 parents, and 25 school administrators – this report documented Boko Haram's attacks on schools, students, and teachers in Borno, Yobe, and Kano states between 2009 and February 2016. It charts the different kinds of assaults waged by the book haram insurgents, including targeted killings, suicide attacks, widespread abduction, burning and looting. Some of these assaults likely amount to war crimes and crimes against humanity. For example, in Borno and Yobe states, the most affected states, schools at all levels have been closed in 22 out of 27 local government areas for at least two years, and public secondary schools in the state capital, Maiduguri, only reopened in February 2016 after internally displaced people, or IDPs, who occupied most of the schools, was relocated elsewhere. Education might have ground to a complete standstill in even relatively safe Maiduguri if it were not for some private schools that remained open when state authorities shut down public schools in March 2014. A similar report by Hawke (2015) revealed that an estimated 3.7 million children need educational support in Nigeria. Additionally, the report suggested that if the educational requirements of these children are not met, an epidemic of chronic educational decay may result. It is necessary to understand how Nigerian children's experiences with Boko Haram have affected their attitude toward schooling as well as their schoolteachers' job performance in relation to assimilation, accommodation, and effective communication before and after being exposed to the Boko Haram insurgency. The September 11, 2001 terrorist attacks introduced a new wave of terrorism that has required new methods of teaching and treatment for the mental health consequences of terrorism. Given that the Nigeria predates the Boko Haram insurgency, it is possible that the provisions in the Act may not cater to the mental health needs of Nigerian children impacted by Boko Haram (Adepelumi, 2018). Exposure to terrorism causes poor concentration problems and low cognitive capacity in children. Children who have experienced severe trauma from violence have weaker school performance, when children are exposed to violence between the ages of 11 to 15 years, their assimilation and adjustment process may be impaired, and they may find it difficult to process new information and can affect teachers' job performance as well (McLeod, 2015). Tunde-Ayinmode et al (2012) and Atilola et al (2015) evaluated the effects of terrorism in Nigeria; however, children are exposed to terrorism in northeastern Nigeria in terms of the psychological academic effects of terrorism, the impact of terrorism on children's educational experience, and how children cope with the trauma of terrorism also has a negative impact on teachers' job performance. The effects of terrorism on children in Nigeria may not be the same as in other parts of the world because of differing political wills, cultural practices, and norms. UNICEF (2016) estimated that 1,200 schools were destroyed, 319,000 child learners were denied access to safe learning spaces, and 952,029 school- aged children were displaced because of the Boko Haram insurgency.

Human Rights Watch (HRW, 2016) reported that Boko Haram, whose name in Hausa, the dominant language in northern Nigeria, means “Western education is forbidden,” has targeted and killed teachers, education workers and students. At least 611 teachers have been deliberately killed and a further 19,000 have been forced to flee since 2009.

A teacher from one village in Northern Borno State, hiding in Maiduguri in fear for his safety, told Amnesty International that there is no opportunity for children in the village to continue their education after the school was forced to close. He, said, “None of the children go to school now, Amnesty International (2013) .Those who were taking exams had to hide their school uniforms in a plastic bag before they leave home. Boko Haram even tore the uniforms of students who travel to Maiduguri to attend school from the village. The entire town was locked down. No movement is allowed in or out. Amnesty International, (2013) stated that the army has banned the use of all forms of transportation even within the town. So, teachers cannot go to school; parents cannot send their children to school because you have to walk, regardless of the distance.

As reported by a Human Rights watch (2015) reported that between June and October 2012, schools in Damagan, Damaturu and Potiskum, Yobe state, bore the brunt of Boko Haram attacks. Yobe Children’s Academy was the first private school to be attacked in Damaturu. On the night of July 22, insurgents burned 32 classrooms and nine offices in the primary and secondary section. A teacher working late in the office was shot and killed after being forced to show the insurgents around the school the local education authority office, and at least eight schools comprise Racecourse Primary School, Nahuta Primary School, Sabon Layi Primary School, Government Day Junior Secondary School, College of Administration and Business Studies, and Best Center Vocational School were attacked.

Boko Haram has been identified as a one of the factors that facilitated various levels of destructions of many economic activities, including distortion of students’ school enrollment attendance and educational infrastructure in most locations in northern Nigeria.

Also Sahara Reporters, (2014) reported that an encounter with a local who confess that” We were confused at first whether the men in military uniform were soldiers or insurgents. Some people fled, but many of us stayed. They gathered all the men at the primary school and began to shoot. Women and children began to run up the hills, but they pursued us. I was hiding with a group of my students who had lost sight of their parents in the confusion when the insurgents came to us. They were shouting, “Where are the men?” Then they asked the children to stand upright. They selected and took away the boys who looked tall enough to be 10 to 12 years old, saying they were old enough to fight. I watched helplessly as they ran uphill with those poor boys shooting and killing for over four hours as they went”. Human Rights Watch (2015) confirmed that when Boko Haram combatants seized control of six villages around Gwoza on June 3, 2014, they sought out men for killing and young boys for recruitment.

From the beginning of 2012, about 70 teachers and more than 1000 school children have been killed while some were wounded; 50 schools were burnt, and more than 60 others have been forced to close. Many children were forced out of school across communities - in Yobe, Borno and Adamawa states. Many teachers were forced to migrate to other locations for safety (The Guardian 2014). According to Odinkalu (2014) the closing down of schools have far reaching consequences, including ending the education of many students and the opportunity to get into higher education. Not fewer than 85 schools were closed in Borno state affecting about 120,000 students after a frequent attack by Islamic militants in areas which has the country’s most illiteracy rate, and more than 200 schoolgirls were kidnapped on the night of April 2014 (The Guardian 2014).

This act is totally inhuman and is totally condemned, which has set Yobe State education backward. Chioma Igbokwe (2015) explained that poorly educated young men and boys, mostly from extremely poor homes, initially embraced membership of the group voluntarily in exchange for financial rewards and the promise of paradise in the afterlife. Chioma Igbokwe (2015) further confirmed that a teenage boy released from military detention in May 2013 said he helped Boko Haram to burn schools which resulted in a reduction in students attendance, enrollment and destruction of school facilities because he was paid the equivalent of US\$25.

Channels Television (February 25, 2014) reported that witnesses said the students were attacked in their hostels at night and slain by the hoodlums instead of the usual gun to avoid the attention of security men within the town. The Federal Government College Buni Yadi is a coeducational institution located some 55 kilometers south of Damaturu the Yobe State capital. Channels Television (2014) also confirmed that the spokesman of the 3 Special Operation Battalion, Damaturu, Capt Eli Lazarus, who confirmed the assault on the innocent students said the casualty figure is yet to be confirmed because of the destruction of telecom masts in Buni- Yadi by the sect. However, the Hausa Service of the British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC) reported that about 29 students were slain during the attack while an unknown number burnt to ashes and the attack finally burnt down the school.

“My Islamic teacher told us that Western education was a sin and working for the government was also a sin. He then asked those who have gone through secondary and university education to destroy their certificates as quoted by Chioma Igbokwe (2015) Abdulwaheed Nasiru. That singular act fully convinced me that if my brothers who attended university can destroy their certificates because of Boko Haram, I should not hesitate”. This implies that not destruction of school facilities, students’ enrollment, attendance and teachers’ job performance by Boko haram insurgency, but also damaging the Nigerian human resources and future manpower.

Ugwumba and Odom (2015) Stated that Education is under attack, as incidents of violence against students, teachers, union, schools and government officials are on the rise worldwide and in Nigeria in particular, Boko Haram insurgency has deliberated raise threat against students, academics, teachers and education facilities create barrier to accessing quality education for all. Ugwumba and Odom (2015) reported that many teachers have been forced to flee for their safety to other states. The highest number of attacks was in Borno state in the North-east when contacted the Nigeria teachers’ union, more than 1000 teachers have been forced to flee from areas in the north since 2012. Based on this backdrop of adverse effect of Boko Haram on education for all (EFA) in Nigeria, one is inclined to ask the question; how can Nigeria at the peak of Boko Haram insurgency arrive at EFA objectives.

BBC and CNN (2014) reported that Boko Haram justified the abductions of school girls as punishment for the girls’ participation in Western education. In a video released in May 2014, Shekau said “women and girls would continue to be abducted to turn them to the path of true Islam and to ensure they did not attend western school”. This terrorist activity has a negative impact on students’ enrollment, attendance especially girls’ child and teachers’ job performance.

Atleast 94 school girls from Government Girls Science and Technical Secondary School at Dapchi town in Bursari local government area of Yobe state are missing after girls burden school was attacked by Islamist militant group Boko Haram. The militants invaded the town on Monday and targeted girls’ school after reaching the town around 7 pm with over 18-gun trucks. A community source told Sahara reporters that at least four bodies of students were recovered from the bush in the nearby town of Kusun. This terrorist activity has weakened the school activities and teachers’ job performance in Yobe State. Saharareporters, (feb 20, 2018)

According to Mohammed, Ibrahim and Suleiman (2017) the emergence of the Boko Haram sect, whose objectives or ideology is to introduce their ideology on the people through bombings, slaughtering, and abduction of human beings, including school students, creating fear and a sense of insecurity in the society has distorted achievement of educational goal and objectives in all levels of education in Yobe State. Sahara reporters (2018) stated that after the head count on Tuesday, it was discovered that at least 94 of the girls were still missing. The school was immediately closed while education authorities and security forces in the state began efforts to locate the missing students.

Yakubu (2012) disclosed that in April 2012 that there were over 9.5 million Almajiri children that are denied the right to basic primary education in Nigeria. Northern Nigeria has suffered a low enrollment rate, especially in the primary education sector. Ruquyyatu (2013) blamed this on the effect of the long-standing effect of Islamic education as most parents are yet to embrace western education. To such parents’ western education is tied to the Bible and it is an indirect way of changing their religion. Patrick and Felix (2013) confirmed that Boko haram have carried out several attacks and issued threats to schools in the Northeast, teachers and students were killed or injured and structure razed. Patrick and Felix (2013)

confirmed that on the 12th of March, 2012, gunmen linked to Boko Haram attacked Hausawa -Danmaliki primary school in the kumboso local government area of Kano state. Several pupils and teachers were killed. In September 2013, a school of Agriculture in Yobe state was also attacked at night by the Boko Haram and more than sixty students were killed. Patrick and Felix (2013). Stated that education is worst hit by the Boko Haram activities. Apart from the fact that the fights directly against western education which is widely practiced in Nigeria with schools established in every nook and cranny of the country, western education has remained the bedrock of human and capital developments in Nigeria.

The problem of this study is the worsening of Boko haram terrorist’s attacks in Borno, Yobe and Adamawa, State which include the loss of manpower or abduction of students, teachers and personnel and damage of buildings and facilities most typical due to the burning, bombing or shelling of buildings or transport facilities by Boko Haram. It is against this background that this study examines the impact of Boko haram insurgency on teachers’ job performance in Colleges of Education in North east, Nigeria.

Eze, Wosu and Agwanwo (2014) believed that Boko haram insurgent strict ideology was enforced by radical religious beliefs, a terrorist outlook, a network of criminal gangs, and a political tool to ‘colonized territories with the aim of propagating their ideology. Mohammed (2014) stated that the trademarks of the Boko Haram or destruction of lives and property with reckless attitudes, through bombings, abduction and slaughtering of human beings especially in the North eastern part of the country and other places. This implies that the threat to education from Boko Haram attack should be seen in the context of the wider problem of the impact of conflict in general on the degradation of education or prevention of educational development. This menace of Boko haram if not well handled by Nigerian authority will not only course educational decay but also destroys the overall national development.

Objectives of the Study

The main objectives of the study is to determine:

- a. The extent of students’ enrolment in school during Boko haram insurgency and teachers’ job performance in Colleges of Education in Northeast Zone, Nigeria.
- b. The level of students’ attendance in school during Boko haram insurgency and teachers’ job performance in Colleges of Education in North East, Nigeria.
- c. The extent of school closure during Boko haram insurgency and teachers’ job performance in Colleges of Education in North East, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide this study:

1. To what extent is the students’ enrollment in school during Boko haram insurgency in Colleges of Education in North East, Nigeria?
2. To what level is the students’ attendance in school during Boko haram insurgency in Colleges of Education in North East, Nigeria?
3. To what extent is the school closure during Boko haram insurgency in Colleges of Education in North East States, Nigeria?

RESULTS AND INTERPRETATION

1: To what extent is the of students’ enrollment in school during Boko haram insurgency in Colleges of Education in North East, Nigeria?

	Statement Strategy	Mean	S. D	Remarks
1.	In the affected area many parents sent their children away or leave their state, which contributed to the low of student’s enrolment.	2.67	1.13	Accept
2.	The source of income of many parents in the study is blocked as a result of insurgency leading to poor enrolment	2.45	1.32	Accept
3	Psychologically, insurgency has contributed to low school’s enrolment.	3.41	1.65	Accept
4.	Teachers select days to attend lectures	3.67	1.46	Accept

The table above discusses the impact of Boko haram insurgency on student enrollment rate in colleges of education in the zone, item (1) is about the role parent played in contributing to poor student enrollment in the schools, many parents have to move their children away from the affected local government which contributed to poor students enrollment in the schools. With 2.67 and 1.13 mean and standard deviation implies that parents contributed to poor enrollment in the schools. This could be due to fear of consistent attack of the sect in the areas. Item (2) tries to investigate the factors responsible that leads to poor enrollment, aside fear of attack, financial strength of parents was also affected as parent loss their jobs and other sources of income such as farming are blocked, this has contributed to poor student enrollment in the schools, with a mean of 2.45 and standard deviation of 1.32 poor financing is a contributing factor in poor student enrolment in the schools. Item (3) is to investigate the psychological effects of the insurgency on both parents, students and teachers and its effects on student enrolment. The result shows that the insurgency affected the entire community and fear of the unknown has brought a high rate of timidity in the communities. With a mean of 3.41 and a standard deviation of 1.65 the respondents are of the opinion that the insurgency has a negative psychological impact on the student enrollment in the schools. Item (4) talks about the laxity of the teachers in performing their duties as teachers select days of attending lectures, the result here shows a mean of 2.44 and standard deviation of 1.25 this means that the insurgency has a negative impact on the teacher’s consistency in service delivery.

2: To what level is the students’ attendance in school during Boko haram insurgency in Colleges of Education in North East, Nigeria?

SN	Statement Strategy	Mean	S.D	Remark
1.	The average students attendance is less than the expected attendance.	3.53	1.31	Accept
2.	My student only come to school between Monday- Wednesday	3.6	1.65	Accept
3	Majority of the students that come to class are the children of the teachers	2.41	1.93	Reject
4	My students no longer have fear of absenteeism anymore	3.36	1.47	Accept
5	Teachers/ lecturers reject appointment if they are posted to one of the area affected by insurgency.	3.12	1.83	Reject

The table above shows the result from research question two (2) discussing about the impact of Boko haram insurgency on student attendance. Item (1) shows that the average attendance in the most of the school is poor with mean of 3.53 and standard deviation of 1.31 shows a poor result. By implication, the insurgency had a negative impact on the student attendance. Item (2) on the other hand highlights the fact that the students and teachers have made it a habit to attend school on certain days of the week. Monday-Wednesday was often the days for teaching and learning, with mean and standard deviation of 3.60 and 1.65 shows a negative impact. Item (3) rejected the statement that say only the children of the teachers attend school, with a mean of 2.41 and standard deviation of 1.93 shows that even though there is poor school attendance by students and teachers there is no specific set of students that attend school. Item (4) is about the students urge and need to attend school. Absenteeism is no longer a thing of concern as teachers no longer punish students for being absent in class. The item shows a mean of 3.36 and standard deviation of 1.47 shows a negative impact of the insurgency on both the students and teachers. Finally, item (5) discusses the rate of teacher’s acceptance or rejection of appointment during the insurgence. This result shows that many teachers accept appointment even though there are crises but that does not stop them from accepting appointment, this can be associated with the fact that north-eastern part of Nigeria is one of the poorest states in the country. According to Abdulrashid, teachers collect salary without working in the affected state, this could be the same reason why appointment letters are accepted by the newly employed in the state.

3: What is the extent of school closure during Boko haram insurgency in Colleges of Education in North East States, Nigeria?

SN	Statement Strategy	Mean	S.D	Remarks
1.	The schools in my locality were temporarily closed	3.86	1.39	Accept
2.	No school closure in my State	2.34	1.98	Reject
3	School closure was observed only in some selected LGA	3.78	1.67	Accept
4	95% of schools in my state were closed	2.34	1.85	Reject
5	The destruction of schools by Boko haram attack has led to the closing down of unaffected schools.	2.34	1.85	Reject

The table above tries to investigate the rate of school closure in the affected areas of the zone, item (1) shows that there was temporary school closure during the insurgency, with 3.86 and 1.39 mean and standard deviation means that many schools were closed and education activities were shut. Similarly item (2) supports the statement with a mean of 2.34 and standard deviation of 1.98. Item (3) support the statement that even though there was school closure in the zone, not all schools were closed, most of the schools closed were the ones in the affected local government are. Item (4) also supports the statement with a mean of 2.34 and standard deviation of 1.85. Similarly item (5) is in agreement with the responses in item 3 and 4. Unaffected schools were allowed to continue with their education system.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This is to acknowledge the Tertiary Education Trust Fund (Tetfund) for funding this research through the Institutional Based Research (IBR) of Umar Suleiman College of Education Gashua, Yobe State

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